

ERASMUS International Academic Research Symposium in Science,
Engineering and Architecture
(April 5-6, 2019 Izmir, Turkey)
PROCEEDING BOOK

ERASMUS Fen, Mühendislik ve Mimarlık Bilimlerinde Uluslararası
Akademik Çalışmalar Sempozyumu
(5-6 Nisan 2019, İzmir, Türkiye)

TAM METİN BİLDİRİ KİTABI

ISBN: 978-605-7602-67-1

Publishing Director / Yayın Yönetmeni: Muhammet Özcan

Editor / Editör: Assoc. Prof. Dr. Levent Uğur

ASOS YAYINEVİ

1st Edition / 1.baskı: July/Temmuz 2019

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ANALYSIS OF THERMODYNAMIC REFRIGERATION MACHINES CYCLES USING CYCLEPAD / Alif DI-AMBU NGIMBI

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Introduction

Cooling plays an important role in many areas of human life. The conditions of high temperature can present a danger for the goods and the people, it is thus people use the cooling by multiple processes known nowadays. In injection molds, for example, the cooling fluid sometimes requires cooling for the good quality of the finished products. The cooling fluid passes through a series of thermodynamic transformation called inverse thermodynamic cycle. Machines operating in inverse thermodynamic cycles to produce refrigeration by the transfer of heat from a lower temperature region to higher temperature one are called refrigerating machines. To realize these machines, we need two sources of heat and work. In addition, there are refrigeration cycles with three heat sources which allow operation without work input: absorption machines. But in this work, we will only focus on the first group.

The refrigeration cycle consists of at least the following 4 elements including an evaporator, a condenser, a compressor and an expansion device (valve or throttle) (Fig.1). The concept of refrigeration is linked to that of heat pumps, depending on whether the useful effect is at the evaporator or the condenser.

Fig.1 Basic refrigeration cycle

The operation of each of these components is based on the property of the refrigerants to evaporate and condense at different temperatures depending on the pressure.

1. The compressor, which compresses the gas causing the temperature to rise.

2. In the expansion device (Throttle), the fluid expands and vaporizes partially and therefore cools to a temperature level that will depend on the application.

3. In the evaporator, the liquid refrigerant boils and evaporates by absorbing heat from the external fluid.

4. In the condenser, the hot gas coming from the compressor will release its heat to the external fluid. The refrigerant then gaseous cools ("desuperheating"), before the appearance of the first drop of liquid.

Calculating thermodynamic cycles by hand is exhausting, difficult and time-consuming. The use of intelligent software for calculating thermodynamic cycles has a great advantage.

In this work, we will analyze two thermodynamic cycles operating with ammonia (NH₃) as refrigerant. The first is a simple machine that must provide 1.5 GJ/h of cooling capacity (417 kW). The temperature at the evaporator should be -10°C and the condenser cooling water at 26°. We will take a temperature difference (ΔT) between the condenser inlet temperature and the refrigerant condensation temperature of about 7°C. The second machine is a two-stage machine (2 compressors and 2 throttles) to provide the same cooling capacity as the first one. The temperature at the inlet of the first compressor (T_1) will be -10°C and 33°C at its outlet (T_2). Les performances des 2 machines seront discutées en utilisant CyclePad.

1. Analyse Of Refrigeration Machines Cycles By Cyclepad

Normally, the calculation in a cycle analysis is complex, lengthy, and tedious for an engineer. The studies will be time-saving and fun for engineers using CyclePad as a tool to help in the cycle analysis, design, and optimization [1]. CyclePad is a thermodynamic software. It enables to construct and analyze a wide variety of thermodynamic cycles. It has been co-developed by Oxford University and Northwestern University since 1995. It works in two modes, build and analysis. In the first mode (Build), we use a graphics editor to place the components and connect them with the others. We enter the second mode (analysis) when CyclePad is convinced that the design is fully developed. At this point, each component is connected by another component via a connector. In the analysis phase, we specify:

- Which working fluid to use;
- The different calculation assumptions;

- Numeric values for components and intermediate states.

Fig.2.Dialog box when opening CyclePad

CyclePad has 12 components for open cycle and 6 components for closed cycle.(Fig.3 and Fig.4).

Fig.3.Component for open cycle

Fig.4.Component for closed cycle

To add a component, just click on it. After adding components, they should be connected to create a cycle. (Fig.5).

Fig.5.Connection of 2 components in CyclePad

At the end of our cycle design, after connecting all the components to each other, we can switch to the analysis mode. A dialog box appears to switch to the analysis mode.

Fig.6. Dialog box to access the analysis mode

In the analysis mode, there is another mode of contradiction that appears when CyclePad detects a conflict.

Fig.7. Contradiction mode dialog box

After an overview of CyclePad, we will now go on to analyze our two cycles. Let's start with the simple machine.

Fig.8. Simple refrigeration cycle.

Let's start with the manual calculation of this cycle. Note that for this study, we will consider perfect transformations. Isentropic compression, isobaric condensation and evaporation, and isenthalpic expansion.

- Compression work W_c . [2]

$$w_c = h_2 - h_1 \text{ (h is the enthalpy)}. \quad (1)$$

$h_1 = ?$ Knowing the evaporation temperature and the state of Ammonia at the inlet of the compressor (Saturated), we find h_1 using the thermodynamic table of Ammonia.

$$\Rightarrow h_1 = 1432 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kg}} \text{ et } s_1 = 5,4730 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kg K}} \text{ (s is the entropy)}.$$

$h_2 = ?$ We already know the temperature (33 ° C) and the state of point 3 (valve inlet is saturated) and by assuming that the condenser is operating isobarically, the pressure in point 3 will be the same as in point 2. Knowing the entropy of point 2 which is the same as that of point 1, we find its enthalpy using the table, using the pressure of point 3. We will have:

After iteration between 32 ° C and 34 ° C, we find

$$p_3 = 12,7448 \text{ bars} \Rightarrow h_2 = 1645,28 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kg}}$$

$$\Rightarrow \Delta h_{1-2} = w_c = h_2 - h_1 = 1645,28 - 1432 = 213,28 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kg}} \quad (2)$$

- Net refrigeration production:

The evaporator operating isobarically it will be:

$$q_f = h_4 - h_1 \quad (3)$$

$h_4 = ?$ knowing $h_3 = 337,45 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kg}}$ as the valve is isenthalpic by assumption,

$$\Rightarrow h_4 = h_3 = 337,45 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kg}} \Rightarrow q_f = |337,45 - 1432| = 1094,55 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kg}}$$

- Efficiency (COP)

$$\varepsilon_f = \frac{q_f}{w_c} = \frac{1094,55}{213,28} = 5,1319 \quad (4)$$

- The mass flow of Ammonia (m dot)

$$\dot{m} = \frac{\dot{Q}_f}{q_f} = \frac{417}{1094,55} = 0,38097 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{s}} \quad (5)$$

After analysis with CyclePad, we found a flow rate of 0.3812 kg/s. The results are presented in the following pictures.

Fig.9. Compressor

Fig.11. Condenser

Fig.13. Outlet of the compressor

Fig.10. Evaporator

Fig.12. Inlet of the compressor

Fig.14.Overall assessment of the cycle

Fig.15. COP according to the evaporation temperature

This analysis (Fig.15) shows that the more we want to lower the temperature at the evaporator, the more costs the cooling because we will need a larger compressor. As a result, industrial refrigeration machines consume more than the refrigeration machines used for air conditioning.

Fig.16. COP according to quality at 1

This curve shows that the machine has a better performance when the fluid entering the compressor is not fully saturated.

Fig.17. COP according to quality at 3

We now find that the machine has better performance when the fluid leaving the condenser is close to liquid saturation.

Fig.18. COP according to T_3

We observe that the performance of the machine is improved when the temperature of the fluid leaving the condenser decreases.

Fig.19. T-S diagram of the cycle.

From the values found above, we can compare, values computed from CyclePad to hand calculation values.

Table 1: Error between hand calculation and Cyclepad values.

	$w_c [\frac{kJ}{kg}]$	$q_f [\frac{kJ}{kg}]$	ϵ_f / COP	Flow rate $\dot{m} [\frac{kg}{s}]$
Hand calculations	213,28	1094,55	5,1319	0,38097
CyclePad values	213,1	1094	5,13	0,3812
Relative error to hnd calculations	0,0008or 0,08 %	0,0005 or 0,05 %	0,0003 or 0,03%	0,0006 or 0,06%

From these values, we realize that the values calculated by Cyclepad are accurate.

Now, let's analyze the complex machine.

This machine is actually, an improved version of the simple machine by adding some additional components.

It is a two-stage machine (2 compressors and 2 valves) to provide 1500 MJ / h. The temperature at the inlet of the first compressor (T_1) will be $-10^\circ C$ and $33^\circ C$ at its outlet (T_2).

The machine has 3 pressure levels. Low pressure, intermediate pressure, and high pressure. Knowing the temperature at the inlet of the low-pressure compressor and since the state of the Ammonia is saturated there, the other quantities are deduced with CyclePad. And knowing the temperature of the state 2 (after the compression), since the compression is

isentropic, the pressure in this state is set by CyclePad or by iterating twice. A first iteration to find the pressure at 40°C equivalent to the entropy of state 1, pressure between 7 bar and 6 bar. A second iteration to find the pressure at 33°C, at the same entropy as state 1, between 30°C and 40°C on the same isentrope. Having found this value, the maximum pressure (High pressure) is found by exploiting theories on the optimal intermediate pressure[10].

$$p_2 = \frac{p_1^2}{p_i} \Rightarrow p_2 = \frac{5,63^2}{2,9} = 10,88 \text{ bars.} \quad (6)$$

To have 417 kW of cooling capacity, an ammonia flow rate of 0.343 kg/s at the low-pressure circuit and about 0.3720 kg/s at the high-pressure circuit are required. These flow rates are lower than that found for the simple machine. For the same cooling capacity, the complex machine is less cumbersome (small components) and consumes less energy ($COP_{\text{complex}} > COP_{\text{simple}}$) compared to the simple machine.

Fig.20. Complex refrigeration cycle

Fig.21.Overall assessment of the cycle

Fig.22.High-pressure compressor

Fig.23.Evaporator

Fig.24.Condenser

Fig.25.Intermediate Condenser

Fig.26.Low-pressure compressor

Sensitivity analysis of some parameters to the variation of others. We will see here how the COP of the machine will be influenced when, for example, the temperature at point 3 (exit of the intermediate condenser) varies from 7 to 30°C.

Fig.27.COP according to the temperature at the exit of the intermediate condenser

We observe that the performance of the machine is better in case the temperature at the exit of the intermediate condenser decreases.

Fig.28.COP according to the temperature at the exit of the low-pressure compressor.

Note that if the temperature at the exit of the LP compressor rises when the other parameters are constant, the COP increases to a maximum. For our exercise, this maximum is around 50°C, where the COP reaches 6.52. At this point, our machine will consume less but the cooling capacity will drop. This implies that it is the Ammoniac flow that must be increased. It will be a question of choosing between cost and the volume of the installation. (Fig.28)

Fig.29.COP according to the maximum pressure.

Increasing the maximum pressure decreases the COP of the machine. If therefore the overall compression ratio decreases, the coefficient of performance of the machine will substantially increase while the cooling capacity will not be affected. (Fig.29).

Fig.30.COP according to the quality of fluid at the inlet of the mixer.

The COP is as good as the quality of the fluid entering the mixer from the separator tends to move away from the gas saturation curve (the quantity of liquid increases).

If we lower the maximum pressure P_5 of the machine without being equal to the intermediate pressure, a little higher (6 bars). The condensation temperature will decrease significantly, the work of the HP compressor will decrease as well. The coefficient of performance will increase and the maximum flow rate of the cycle will decrease. And therefore the energy cost will decrease.

Fig.31.COP according to the temperature at the exit of the intermediate condenser.

The sensibly analysis shows that the temperature at the exit of the intermediate condenser influences the performance of the machine. When this temperature is decreased to a certain range the COP increases. If this temperature can be decreased to be close enough to the temperature at 10 (7°C). Let's set it 8°C. The COP of the machine is close to 12,86 (See Fig.34).

Fig.32. Temperature of condensation of the simple machine set to be equal to the temperature of condensation of the complex machine. (9,28°C)

Fig.33.New result for the simple machine cycle.

Fig.34.New result for the simple machine cycle.

Table 2: Comparison between the simple and complex machine.

Parameters	Summary of the simple machine for 1500 MJ/h of cooling capacity	Summary of the complex machine for 1500 MJ/h of cooling capacity
Max flow rate	0,3454 kg/s	0.3454 kg/s
COP	12,58	12,86
Condensation temperature	9,28°C	9,28°C
Evaporation temperature	-10°C	-10°C

The results of this table show that for the same cooling capacity, same condensation and evaporation temperatures, the complex machine has better a coefficient of performance than the simple machine. The simple machine would, therefore, consume more than the complex machine, while the refrigerant flow rate will be the same.

Conclusion

This work presented the analysis of 2 thermodynamic cycles of refrigerating machines using the potentialities of CyclePad. At the end of this study, we presented some points of these cycles that influence the performance of these machines. It will, therefore, be useful for the designers of these types of machines to exploit this information for finished products of quality with low consumption.

This study showed that:

- The values calculated by Cyclepad are accurate.
- The machine simple has a better performance when the fluid entering the compressor is not fully saturated.
- The machine simple has better performance when the fluid leaving the condenser is close to liquid saturation.
- The performance of the machine complex is improved when the temperature of the fluid leaving the condenser decreases.
- Increasing the maximum pressure decreases the COP of the machine.
- The COP of the machine complex is as good as the quality of the fluid entering the mixer from the separator tends to move away from the gas saturation curve.
- the complex machine has better a coefficient of performance than the simple machine.

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